

The Coupling Constant Series and Bosons Commutation

O Manor

April 23, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework, 8T, and the insights gain regarding the nature of bosons, and in particular the photon, γ , which is represented in the 8T framework as a net variation $N_V = (+5)$, on the coupling term describing the Electric. Analysis of the Bosonic behavior will be made using a varying Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g_E)$ with signature (3,1), which is the connected Einstein manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times R$, by the Euler Lagrange operator. The main tool of analysis is done via primordial coupling constant series on the manifold, derived in early 2021.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Examine the term describing the electric coupling. We proved majestic (3) is the electron in the 8-Theory thesis. The photon is represented as net variation, which is unbound. It is free to propagate all across the manifold.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + 5 \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.121)$$

Suppose such a photon just propagated from the electron. i.e. the majestic (3). The meaning of such an occurrence is that there is a net curvature that is unbound on the manifold. Such curvature will effect all other potential propagation toward itself. It will create a pull effect on other potential boson propagating from fermions. That is in agreement with what we know about the commutation relation of bosons, and the fact that the probability to find a boson increase if there is already a boson in a certain position of the matrix. The innovative part of this paper and the main point to take is the new setting, a in which a photon itself is a net curvature causing other curvature propagating at later time to converge to its position. When analyzed via the new framework it than becomes quite easy to understand what is going on at that fundamental level.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_i > 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i > 0 \quad (2.1)$$

The point of view presented is not presented in quantum field theory framework, the methods they use to describe the commutation and anti-commutation is VOA, vertex of algebra, and there is simply no way to imagine or to grasp the intuitive reason for the such a behavior. By using an approach combining manifolds and variation, i.e. Euler Lagrange, it is possible to explain the behavior of bosons in an intuitive and simpler fashion. It is possible to state that each boson is creating a "gravitational effect", i.e. curvature on the manifold, and thus increase the probability of arrival for other bosons to itself.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)